

Performance of rice genotypes in coastal saline soil, India.

Designation	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/hill (no.)	Panicle length (cm)	Filled spikelets/panicle (no.)	Spikelet sterility (%)	Days to heading (no.)	Plant survival at maturity (%)	Salinity tolerance score		Grain yield (kg/plot)
								Vegetative	Maturity	
CSR4	71	19	15.8	78	27	81	91	4	3	0.7
C100	65	16	16.8	80	41	102	81	4	4	0.9
C14-1	78	12	20.1	90	25	102	95	3	3	1.0
IR10198-66-2	85	16	22.7	85	12	105	85	4	4	0.8
IR2053-436-1-2	91	14	18.1	93	29	107	80	5	4	0.7
IR36	64	18	17.3	71	32	106	76	5	4	0.4
IR4227-109-1-2-3	81	14	19.1	71	29	104	89	4	4	0.7
IR4422-6-2	83	12	21.0	81	35	114	95	3	3	0.7
PNL 5-30	71	16	18.0	68	44	111	81	4	5	0.7
IR4432-28-5	79	19	20.2	68	47	111	84	5	5	0.8
IR4595-4-1-13	75	9	18.5	64	39	115	99	4	4	0.4
IR4630-22-2-17	83	11	19.9	70	18	113	97	3	4	0.8
IR4630-22-2-5-1-3	85	11	19.0	68	28	108	94	4	3	0.8
IR50	66	19	15.6	67	25	96	73	7	7	0.6
IR8241-B-B650-2	127	14	20.6	64	31	103	92	4	5	0.6
IR8608-189-2-2-1-3	68	16	19.0	55	23	93	85	4	4	0.5
IR8608-298-3-1-1-2	72	19	19.0	67	24	89	89	4	4	0.8
IR9575 Sel	90	11	21.1	104	27	113	87	5	4	0.8
IR9732-119-3	75	19	19.1	99	33	102	79	5	5	0.9
Pokkali (resistant check)	119	17	20.1	70	17	104	83	6	4	0.5
IR9884-54-3	78	13	19.8	84	30	134	88	4	4	0.3
PNL-11-2	71	19	18.0	78	31	111	88	4	4	0.5
CSR1 (local check)	99	18	17.8	69	21	96	99	3	3	1.4
CSR3 (local check)	101	15	18.2	88	14	98	96	3	3	1.3
CSR6 (local check)	118	14	21.0	77	31	110	99	3	3	1.2

^a Standard Evaluation System for Rice, IRRI, 1980.

CSR4, IR36, IR4595-4-1-13, IR9884-54-3, and PNL-11-2 were scored 4 at maturity. Spikelet sterility of these genotypes ranged from 27 to 39% and survival rate from 76 to 99%. CSR4 gave the highest yield. Other entries whose tolerance scores remained almost the same at both stages but whose

survival was more than 80% are also considered tolerant at maturity.

Some entries were scored 4 or 5 (tolerant) at the vegetative stage. Although they had survival rates greater than 75%, their tolerance at maturity decreased. Spikelet sterility in these entries was as high as those of entries

such as PNL5-30 and IR4432-28-5.

Tolerance scores at vegetative stage and at maturity highly but negatively correlated ($r = -0.58^{**}$) with plot yield, as did spikelet sterility ($r = -0.48^{**}$). Only plant survival at maturity was highly and positively correlated with yield ($r = 0.60^{**}$). *ℒ*

Chemical tests for screening rice genotypes tolerant of Zn deficiency under calcareous Fluvents

B. P. Singh, Indian Council of Agricultural Research Complex for NEH Region, Agronomy Division, Bishnupur, Shillong 793004, India; and B. N. Singh, Genetics and Plant Breeding Department, and M. K. Sinha, Soil Science and Agricultural Chemistry Department, Hajendra Agricultural University, Pusa, Samastipur, Bihar 848125, India

In Fluvent soils in North Bihar, India, Zn deficiency is largely caused by calcareous conditions. More than 75% of soils have low Zn. We evaluated 19 semidwarf indica rices for tolerance for Zn deficiency in calcareous Fluvents and

evaluated chemical tests for screening Zn-efficient genotypes at the Sugarcane Research Institute Farm, RAU, Pusa, in 1982.

Soil was a calcareous sandy loam with pH 8.5, EC 0.48 dS/m, 0.45% organic C, 37.5% free CaCO₃, DTPA Zn 0.35 mg/kg, and DTPA Fe 9.10 mg/kg soil. Twenty-five-day-old seedlings were transplanted in 14.4-m² plots in a randomized block design with 3 replications. NPK was applied basally at 60-22-33 mg/kg soil as urea, triple superphosphate, and muriate of potash.

Tolerance for Zn deficiency was visually scored by the 1976 *Standard evaluation system for rice*. For chemical analysis, 25 plants were taken from each plot 30 d after transplanting. Samples

were washed in acidified detergent solution and rinsed with deionized water. Shoots were dried in a forced-air circulation oven at 65° C and dry matter yield was recorded. The 3d and 4th leaves from the top of plants were separated and pulverized in a Waring blender and digested in HNO₃: HClO₄: H₂SO₄. Zn and Fe were determined in the clear aliquot with an atomic absorption spectrophotometer and P was determined colorimetrically.

In most varieties, visual symptoms of Zn deficiency developed 10-15 d after transplanting. Symptoms appeared first on the 3d and 4th leaves and gradually extended to lower leaves. Light yellow spots at the base of leaves were early symptoms. They later coalesced to give

a rusty brown appearance. Plants were stunted and affected foliage dried. Zn deficiency symptoms varied widely among varieties. Percentages of affected hills were averaged and varieties were grouped as tolerant (less than 3% affected hills), moderately tolerant (5-25% affected hills), susceptible (25-50% affected), and highly susceptible (50-100%). Only RAU4009-3 and RAU4005-26 were tolerant.

Shoot dry matter accumulation was markedly reduced by increasing Zn deficiency. Shoot weight, Zn concentration, P to Zn and Fe to Zn concentration ratio are in the table. Zn concentration was between 12.8 and 45.0 ppm, and was positively and significantly correlated with shoot yield ($r = 0.97^{**}$). There was a significant negative correlation with P:Zn (-0.95^{**}) and Fe:Zn (-0.97^{**}) concentration. Zn concentration was below the critical 19 ppm in highly susceptible varieties. Tolerant varieties had P:Zn > 192 and Fe:Zn > 7.6.

About 97% of the variability ($R^2 = 0.969^{**}$) in Zn responses was attributed to Zn concentration and P:Zn and Fe:Zn. The contribution of Zn and P:Zn are shown in the multiple regression equation

$$Y = 4.375 + 0.05^{**} X_1 + 0.014 X_2 + 6.286 X_3 \times 10^{-3^{**}}$$

Where,

Y = shoot yield,

X_1 = Zn content,

X_2 = Fe:Zn, and

X_3 = P:Zn.

(** denotes significance at 1 %)

Fe:Zn, however, did not contribute significantly to variability in Zn deficiency tolerance.

The study showed that Zn concentration and P:Zn could be a reliable tool for screening Zn-efficient varieties. $\mathcal{J}$

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Reaction of rice varieties grown in highly calcareous Fluvents to Zn deficiency, Bihar, India.

Variety	Reaction ^a	Shoot yield (t/15 plants)	Zn concentration (mg/kg)	P:Zn	Fe:Zn
RAU4009-3	T	0.6	41.6	132	6.0
RAU4005-26	T	0.6	45.0	129	5.7
IET6155	M	0.5	30.2	192	7.5
UPR82-1-7	M	0.5	33.5	176	7.3
RAU32-2-1	M	0.5	32.8	180	7.6
IR2071-586-5-6-3	M	0.5	35.0	171	6.7
IR36	S	0.4	20.6	286	13.8
IET4786	S	0.4	21.0	290	13.6
IET2881	S	0.4	22.6	265	12.8
Ratana	S	0.5	24.0	258	12.0
Prasad	S	0.4	23.5	255	11.1
Saket 4	S	0.4	20.5	317	12.2
Rajendra Dhan 201	H	0.3	15.5	406	16.5
Sita	H	0.3	13.5	459	19.1
IET3273	H	0.2	12.8	500	23.1
UPR304-40-2	H	0.3	16.5	388	18.2
UPR231-28-1-2	H	0.3	14.5	455	22.4
Pusa 33	H	0.3	18.5	351	16.4
Pusa 2-21	H	0.3	19.0	331	15.0

^aT = tolerant, M = moderately tolerant, S = susceptible, H = highly susceptible.

Varietal evaluation of rice in waterlogged saline soil

T.S. Sinha and A.K. Bandyopadhyaya, Central Soil Salinity Research Institute (CSSRI), Karnal 132001, Haryana, India

Uniform variety trial-5 comprising 21 entries [including 2 local checks, Kalamota (sel), and SR26B], 8 genotypes found superior during the 1983 trial, and Pankaj (high yielding check) were evaluated at CSSRI,

Performance of 30 promising entries in waterlogged saline soil. Haryana, India. 1985.

Designation	Plant ht (cm)	Panicles/m ²	Days to flowering	Spikelet sterility (%)	Plant survival at maturity (%)	Yield (g/plot)
CR117-215	105	75	137	38.7	7	15
CR292-5258	103	135	145	77.6	11	08
CR292-7050	109	100	140	39.4	12	40
CR221-1030	108	100	139	35.8	8	22
CN499-160-2-1	114	108	135	26.3	9	22
CN499-160-13-6	111	100	136	25.3	6	80
CN506-147-14-1	119	95	141	29.4	20	63
CN506-147-14-2	97	47	143	38.0	4	15
RPAR7360	—	—	—	—	0	—
NC498	118	117	172	17.3	24	147
OR456-30	122	67	140	51.1	14	15
TCA212	133	111	130	16.8	60	78
WC490	137	95	138	23.1	28	115
WC497	130	94	140	11.0	29	85
NC519	127	89	140	17.8	12	43
TCA72	139	108	128	22.4	44	160
PLA1100	—	—	—	—	0	—
NC513	124	78	140	31.3	44	153
NC492	137	142	137	18.1	56	348
Kalamota (sel)	139	105	136	13.4	68	392
SR26B	137	108	135	14.7	85	743
NC487/77	134	103	170	14.3	86	490
NC491	153	92	137	14.0	91	780
NC540	155	102	132	12.8	95	227
BKNPR-7601-4-1-2-3	150	89	145	62.0	81	250
BKNFR7601-4-1-9-2	146	91	136	40.6	88	345
SPR7295-53-1-2-1-2	123	81	144	31.0	90	212
Bowrah	125	61	135	23.6	40	157
IET6905	131	108	133	37.7	80	352
Pankaj	97	75	146	38.2	5	40
CD at 1%	—	54	—	33.2	25.4	297